

Synthesis of substituted pyrrolo[1,2-*a*]pyridines

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2-(2'-Thienyl)pyrrolo[1,2-*a*]pyridine has been synthesised by the reaction of 2-(*w*-bromoacetyl)thiophene (prepared by bromination of 2-acylthiophene) with 2-picoline. Similarly, 2-(4'-methylphenyl)pyrrolo[1,2-*a*]pyridine has been synthesised by the reaction of 4-methylphenacyl bromide with 2-picoline.

Literature survey reveals that azaindenes¹⁻⁵ have been prepared but scanty attention has been given to prepare heteroaromatic substituted azaindenes specially with sulphur as heteroatom. Thus it was thought worthwhile to prepare thiophene substituted azaindene. 2-Acylthiophene (1) on bromination gave 2-(*w*-bromoacetyl)thiophene (2) which was then reacted with 2-picoline followed by basification to afford 2-(2'-thienyl)pyrrolo[1,2-*a*]pyridine (3; Scheme 1). The formation of 3 was confirmed by its 90 MHz PMR spectrum.

2-Substituted phenylazaindenes have been prepared in this laboratory⁶. However, in order to cover the gap, 2-picoline was treated with 4-methylphenacyl bromide (4) in the usual manner to obtain 2-(4'-methylphenyl)pyrrolo[1,2-*a*]pyridine (5; Scheme 1). The structure of 5 was confirmed by its 90 MHz PMR spectrum.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. PMR spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer using internal standard.

Bromination of 2-acetylthiophene :

To a cold solution of 2-acetylthiophene⁷ (1; 1.26 g, 0.01 mol) in CCl₄ (30 ml) was gradually added, with continuous stirring, bromine (0.8 g, 0.01 mol) in CCl₄ (10 ml) during a period of 30 min at 0°. The reaction mixture was slowly taken to RT and stirring continued for another 30 min until evolution of HBr gas ceased. Then HBr and the solvent were removed under reduced pressure to yield the product.

Preparation of 2-(2'-thienyl)pyrrolo[1,2-*a*]pyridine (III) :

2-Picoline (0.93 g, 0.01 mol) was added gradually with shaking to a solution of 2-(*w*-bromoacetyl)thiophene (2; 2.05 g, 0.01 mol) in benzene (30 ml). The mixture was refluxed and the resulting solid dissolved in minimum

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) Anhyd. AlCl₃, (ii) Br/CCl₄, (iii) 2-picoline.

quantity of water and extracted with chloroform. Basification of the above solution with aqueous ammonia resulted in the separation of a solid which was washed with cold water and crystallised from chloroform-ethanol mixture (1.19 g, 60%, m.p. 174–175°) (Found : C, 72.34; H, 4.56; N, 7.08; S, 16.10. Calcd. for C₁₂H₉NS : C, 72.36; H, 4.52; N, 7.04; S, 16.08%); δ (CDCl₃) 7.75 (1H, dd, *J* 4.5 and 2.0 Hz, H-7), 7.40–7.25 (1H, m, H-4), 7.15 (H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, H-1), 7.20–6.95 (3H, m, H-3'/H-4'/H-5' of thiophene), 6.60 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, H-3), 6.70–6.30 (2H, m, H-5/H-6).

p-Methylacetophenone :

To a mixture of sodium-dried toluene (12.6 g, 0.137

mol and anhyd. aluminium chloride (7.8 g) was added distilled acetic anhydride (2.5 g, 0.025 mol) slowly with continuous stirring. The mixture was heated on a water-bath, with continuous stirring for 30 min, cooled to RT and poured into a mixture of crushed ice (150 g) and conc. HCl (150 ml). The solution was then stirred until the aluminium salt dissolved completely. The toluene layer was separated, washed with water, then with two portions of 10% NaOH solution and finally with water. The residual solution was dried over anhyd. magnesium sulfate and the product was collected by distillation at 93–94°/7 mm (14.46 g, 79%), b.p. 223–224°.

2-(4'-Methylphenyl)pyrrolo[1,2-a]pyridine (5) :

p-Methylacetophenone (1.30 g, 0.01 mol) in carbon-tetrachloride (30 ml) was reacted with bromine (0.8 g, 0.01 mol) in carbontetrachloride (10 ml) to form *p*-methylphenacylbromide (4) which was directly treated with 2-picoline (0.93 g, 0.01 mol) in benzene (30 ml). The mixture was refluxed and the resulting solid dissolved in minimum quantity of water and extracted with chloroform. Basification of above solution with aqueous ammonia resulted in the separation of a solid which was washed with cold water and crystallized from chloro-

form-pet. ether mixture (1.55 g, 75%), m.p. 201–202° (Found : C, 86.93; H, 6.30; N, 6.78. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₃N : C, 86.96; H, 6.28; N, 6.76%); δ (CDCl₃) 7.90 (1H, dd, *J* 4.5 and 2.0 Hz, H-7), 7.60 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-2'/H-6'), 7.50 (1H, dd, H-4), 7.40 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, H-1), 7.25 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-3'/H-5'), 6.70 (1H, *J* 1.5 Hz, H-3), 6.80–6.40 (2H, m, H-5/H-6) 2.25 (3H, s, C-4'-Me).

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References

1. P. Molma, P. M. Fresneda and M. C. Lajora, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1985, **22**, 113.
2. Y. Tominaga, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1989, **26**, 1167.
3. Y. Miki, Y. Hiroishi and H. Hachikan, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1991, **28**, 45.
4. H. Stelter and J. Krasselt, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1977, **14**, 573.
5. M. A. Barys, F. M. Abdel-Latif, A. M. Aref and K. U. Sadek, *Heterocyclic Communications*, 2002, **8**, 299.
6. Punil Ghai, Ph.D. Thesis, M. D. University, Rohtak, 1991.
7. A. I. Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", E.L.B.S., 1978, p. 776.